

Research Article

From Paper to Pixels: The Key to Entrepreneurs' Global Success

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Abstract: Entrepreneurs who are economically disadvantaged can significantly impact their ability to succeed in business. Many poor entrepreneurs have limited formal education and may lack basic business skills such as accounting and financial management, marketing, and strategic planning. This can hinder their ability to make informed decisions and effectively run their businesses. Understanding basic accounting principles and practices can be challenging without proper education or training, which is often lacking among the hardcore poor. Thus, they resort to traditional accounting modules in the market. However, the traditional written accounting modules are not only costly and cumbersome, they are also incomprehensible to many due to the technical jargons are language barriers. This lack of effective and financial management tools contributes to the persistence of poverty among these entrepreneurs. To address these challenges, there is a need for accessible and easy-to-use accounting tools specifically tailored to the needs and constraints of entrepreneurs among the hardcore poor. The outcome of this project is an eBook that fills this gap. It is cost-effective, easily accessible, and meticulously prepared to ensure that it is comprehensible to entrepreneurs with no accounting background. The eBook would enable them to prepare accounting records to enable them to make good financial decisions which can then lead to better business performance.

Keywords: accounting, digitalization, eBook, entrepreneurs, financial management

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1. INTRODUCTION

Economically disadvantaged entrepreneurs often face significant barriers that impact their ability to perform well in business. Apart from limited capital, many of them are also lacking in terms of formal education and basic business skills such as accounting, financial management, marketing, and strategic planning. These can severely limit their ability to make informed decisions and run their businesses effectively. The majority of them underestimate the importance of accounting and bookkeeping for internal management and decision-making (Johari et al., 2023). Many of these entrepreneurs struggle to maintain accurate financial records, partly due to the unavailability of accessible, user-friendly accounting tools. Due to the lack of proper education or training, understanding basic accounting principles and practices can be a real challenge to many. As a result, these entrepreneurs use traditional written accounting modules to help them. However, the traditional

written accounting modules are not only costly, but also cumbersome and require storage space. In addition, many of the modules were written using technical jargons which may be difficult to understand. This lack of effective accounting and financial management tools contributes to the persistence of poverty among these entrepreneurs. Prior literature indicates that entrepreneurs without accounting and financial management skills often fail to understand the basic financial concept and would spend more on expenses and incur more losses (Agyapong & Attram, 2019 Tuffour, et al., 2020). Therefore, there is a pressing need for accounting tools that are both accessible and easy to use, and specifically designed for the economically disadvantaged entrepreneurs.

This project is a continuation of a study on income generation among hardcore poor entrepreneurs in Kelantan. The main objective is to create a comprehensive module utilizing digital skills to help participants escape poverty. The key innovation in this project is the transformation of the traditional written accounting module into an eBook format. Designed for ease of use, it addresses the specific needs of these entrepreneurs. The eBook module represents a transformation from paper to pixels and is specifically designed for entrepreneurs within the hardcore poor demographic. Tumba et al., (2022) highlights the necessity of providing ongoing education and workshops on financial concepts, including bookkeeping, cash forecasting, and market volatilities to poor entrepreneurs to elevate their knowledge, which in turn help them to attain good business performance.

2. METHOD AND MATERIAL

Transforming a traditional written accounting module into an eBook format involves digitizing the content and converting handwritten or printed information into electronic text and images. A scanner is used to create digital copies of each page of the paper documents and ensure the scans are clear and legible. The scanned documents are then saved and OCR-processed text as digital files in PDF. The eBook is then structured into chapters and sections based on the content such as on journals, ledgers and financial statements. The content is formatted using eBook creation software or tools to format the content professionally for readability on digital screens by using consistent fonts, headings, and spacing to ensure that diagrams, tables, and other visual elements are clear and properly aligned.

Thus, this eBook format offers an affordable, accessible solution with simplified language and interactive features, enhancing financial literacy and management. By converting the traditional written accounting module into an eBook format, it can preserve the essence of manual accounting practices while leveraging the advantages of digital technology. This approach not only facilitates easier access and distribution but also enhances the potential for interactive learning and engagement with the content. More importantly, it is less costly, does not require large storage space and can be easily upgraded when needed.

3. FINDINGS

By addressing the specific needs of hardcore poor entrepreneurs in Kelantan, this eBook module is specifically designed for simplicity and ease of use, making it accessible even to those with little financial expertise. The eBook format makes the module easily accessible to entrepreneurs and small business owners with a straightforward and affordable solution for managing their finances and bookkeeping. This format is also more practical for users with limited literacy skills as it uses straightforward, easy-to-understand language with minimal technical jargons. Digital tools and interactive features will simplify complex accounting concepts, making them easier to understand and apply. Entrepreneurs will be equipped with practical skills to maintain accurate financial records, leading to better financial health and business sustainability.

Given the large number of small businesses lacking adequate accounting and financial management tools, there is a significant market potential for this module. Small businesses especially those operated by hardcore poor entrepreneurs often face significant challenges in maintaining

adequate financial management due to limited resources and expertise. By equipping hardcore poor entrepreneurs with essential accounting knowledge, the eBook could support their journey toward financial independence and business success, contributing to economic development and reducing poverty. The shift towards digital tools and online learning has accelerated, especially in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic where entrepreneurs are looking for accessible and user-friendly digital resources to enhance their skills. Thus, this eBook provides a practical and efficient solution for entrepreneurs and small business owners who might otherwise struggle with traditional and more complex accounting modules. This is also consistent with findings from prior literature that the combination of digital technology and financial skills (known as techno-finance literacy) is vital to meet the current demands of rapid digitalization of business (Kulathunga et al., 2020).

4. DISCUSSION

The dynamic landscape of entrepreneurship is influenced by a multitude of elements, such as global developments, technological breakthroughs, and cultural transformations (Hayat & Nawi, 2024). Thus, entrepreneurs are actively seeking digital resources that are affordable, comprehensive, interactive and engaging and continuously updated which reflecting the latest trends and best practices.

The marketability of this eBook is significantly enhanced by the collaboration with the Kelantan State Development Office, *Unit Penyelarasan Pelaksanaan, Jabatan Perdana Menteri* (ICU JPM), which has allocated a grant for the Digital Marketing Empowerment Program 2024 (DiME 2024). This initiative aligns with the ICU's primary objective under the Digital Entrepreneur Pioneer Program, which focuses on providing training, guidance, and mentoring to entrepreneurs, enabling them to digitize their business operations. The initiative also aims to boost productivity, improve profit margins, and elevate entrepreneurs from digital poverty by integrating them into the digital economy. The ICU's funding and extensive reach will help ensure the eBook's wide distribution, effectively addressing accessibility challenges among the target audience.

Additionally, the eBook accounting module has the potential to significantly impact various segments of the entrepreneurial community particularly those facing economic hardships. The target market for the module includes small business owners, rural entrepreneurs, women entrepreneurs, youth entrepreneurs, NGOs, educational institutions and government agencies. By addressing the specific needs of diverse entrepreneurial segments, it contributes to the overall goal of reducing economic hardships and fostering sustainable business practices. The module has the potential to bring lasting positive change in the entrepreneurial landscape, whether through direct use by entrepreneurs or as part of larger educational and development programs.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this project represents a significant step towards empowering hardcore poor entrepreneurs in Kelantan through digital innovation. By transforming a traditional accounting module into an engaging and easily comprehensible eBook, the project not only addresses critical challenges but also provides sustainable solutions for financial management and income generation among entrepreneurs. The eBook can be easily marketable as it is less costly than the printed books, but with more attractive and engaging features. It requires less storage space, environmentally friendly, and can be easily accessible anywhere. In addition, the eBook can also be easily updated and upgraded. In line with the digitalization era, this eBook has huge potential to help entrepreneurs in their business quests to enable them to achieve good business performance and compete globally.

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